

New Paradigm in Health Law Education and Regulation; a Conceptual Approach Towards Indonesian National Health Law

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 23, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Health Law, Law Education, Regulations, National Health Law, Law Reformation, Indonesia</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5598983</p>	<p><i>Indonesia has had its health law since 1992. However, the study of health law itself has never been comprehensive enough. Following the many cases involved during the Covid-19 Pandemic, there is a need to have a complete understanding of health law. This leads to the need for systematic learning of health law which shall be in line with the promulgated laws and regulations. The research aims to elaborate and describe the new paradigm in learning health law using conceptual and statutory approaches. This research is qualitative research using secondary data. Analysis was conducted through content analysis of the relevant available data. The discussion showed that to have full knowledge of health law, all aspects of health law must be well understood. It must be viewed from all aspects of laws. The research recommends that the study and learning of health law must be conducted in several major subjects that should be related to the others. Finally, the research will provide a new horizon of Indonesian National Health Law, which eventually needs a reformation of current health laws and regulations.</i></p>

Introduction

The development of Indonesian health law should not be separated from the regulations of the health law that were issued and enforceable from time to time. There were not many regulations that can be found during the Dutch Indie, the era before the independence of the Republic of Indonesia. From preliminary research conducted through the laws issued after the independence, the researcher found that there were only three laws mentioned. They were *Verdoovende Middelen Ordonnantie* (Staatsblad 1927 No. 278 Jo No. 536 as may be amended from time to time), *Het Reglement op den Dienst der Volksgezondheid* (Staatsblad 1882 No. 97 as may be amended from time to time, the latest was with Staatsblad 1949 No. 228), *Het Reglement op het Krankzinnigenwezen* (Staatsblad. 1897 No. 54 as may be amended from time to time). Their existence after independence is due to the application of Article II of transition rules of the original Indonesian Constitution of 1945 before the amendments (1945 Constitution). Further based on Article IV of transition rules of 1945 Constitution, the President of the Republic of Indonesia issued Government Regulation No.2 the Year 1945 that determine all state institutions and regulations that exist before the independence, before it is replaced according to the 1945 Constitution remained in-force unless it violated the 1945 Constitution. The Government Regulation was signed on 10 October 1945.

Besides those three laws that were specifically may be referred to as part of health law, the researcher also found several regulations that were known as general laws, that were still used in handling health issues or matters until today. They are the *Wetboek van Strafrecht voor Nederlands-Indië* (further known as Indonesian Penal Code), *Burgerlijk Wetboek voor Indonesie* (known as Indonesian Civil Code), and *Herziene Indonesisch Reglement* (HIR) (applicable for Java and Madura) and *Reglement Voor de Buitengewesten* (RBg) (applicable for outside Java and Madura) (currently known and used as Indonesian Civil Procedural Law). part of the HIR and RBg that was used in Criminal Procedural Law was replaced by Indonesian national law in 1981. By Indonesian national law is the law that was issued and promulgated after the independence, either as a new law or as a replacement to the old Dutch Indie law.

This research aims to elaborate on the history and development of health law regulations that are relevant to conceptually redetermine the new national health law for Indonesia.

Method

This research is qualitative research using grounded theory with the purpose to find the new concept of the health law. The research used secondary data, which are data available to the public, mainly consisted of primary legal sources. They are laws and regulations enforceable in Indonesia from independence until June 2021 that are related to health.

To find the data required for the research, the researcher used an internet facility to search through “google search machine” using the keywords i.e. *hukum* (law), *kesehatan* (health), *kedokteran* (medical), *undang-undang* (laws), *peraturan* (regulations), and *keputusan* (decree). The researcher would collect the legislations in forms of laws, government regulations, presidential regulations, presidential decrees, minister of health regulations, minister of health decrees, and government bodies regulations as may be related to health or healthcare. Besides the primary legal sources, the researcher also seeks secondary legal sources to be used as triangulation of the validity of the total data and reliability of the grounded theory analysis.

By using content analysis, the researcher reduced the data into legislations that are currently in force. Legislations that have been replaced were taken out for further analysis. However, the amended legislation are still used and makes them part of the amending legislation. They were no exact amount of legislation that was targeted. The search will be stopped when the researcher finds out that the required data for determining the concept of health care law has been achieved. To maintain the validity and reliability of the research, data triangulation was conducted. Some secondary legal sources may be used as relevant data to support the grounded theory. The grounded theory is built based on prior researches that have been conducted by the researcher and published in many journals. Those previous research will support the development of the grounded theory to reach a new paradigm in the study of the health law. It will finally require comprehensive amendment toward current legislation in health law.

Further analysis was conducted using the inductive method, by generalizing the collected data. Data clustering was made for easy reference that may lead to the conclusion of the new concept of the health law. The terms “law” in “health law” were used in a different meaning from “Law” as part of legislations used as data in this research, such as Law No.36 the Year 2009 regarding Health (the Health Law).

Finding

From the google search, the researcher found 52 laws, 64 government regulations, 51 president regulations, 43 president decrees, 132 minister of health regulations, 66 minister of health decree, and 74 regulations that were issued by government bodies that related to health. Through the content analysis of those legislations, as may be predicted, the legislations below the laws were referred and can be traced to the currently enforceable laws. However, there were some government regulations, presidential decrees, or minister of health decrees that were existed before the establishment of the laws. The result of the content analysis showed that there were at least 31 laws that were found to be still effective and enforceable today. Two of them were established and therefore belonged to the era of Dutch Indies, not including the *Wetboek van Strafrecht voor Nederlands-Indië* (Indonesian Penal Code), *Burgerlijk Wetboek voor Indonesie* (Indonesian Civil Code), *Herziene Indonesich Reglement* (HIR) (applicable for Java and Madura) and *Reglement Voor de Buitengewesten* (RBG) (Indonesian Civil Procedure Law). Some of the laws are the laws amending the previous laws there were still effective and enforceable, such as Law No.11 the Year 2020 regarding Job Creation, that amended several laws such as Law No.5 the Year 1997 regarding Psychotropic, Law No.40 the Year 2004 regarding National Social Security System, Law No.44 the Year 2004 regarding Hospital, Law No. 35 the Year 2009 regarding Narcotic, Law No.36 the Year 2009 regarding Health, Law No.24 the Year 2011 regarding Social Health Insurance Administration Body, Law No.18 the Year 2012 regarding Food, Law No.33 the Year 2014 regarding Halal Product Assurance, and Law No.11 The Year 2019 regarding National System of Science and Technology. Below are the laws in the order of their number and year of issuance.

1. Stam Law (*Stoom Ordonnantie*) (State Gazette No.225 the Year 1930);
2. Drug Law (State Gazette No. 419 the Year 1949);
3. Law No.1 the Year 1970 regarding Occupational Safety (State Gazette No.1 the Year 1970, Supplement No.2918);
4. Law No.8 the Year 1976 regarding the Ratification of Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs, 1961 and its amending Protocol (Protocol Amending the Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs, 1961) (State Gazette No.36 the Year 1976, Supplement No.3085);
5. Law No.4 the Year 1984 regarding Infectious Disease Outbreak (State Gazette No.20 the Year 1984, Supplement No.3273);
6. Law No.8 the Year 1996 regarding the Ratification of Convention on Psychotropic Substances 1971 (State Gazette No.100 the Year 1996, Supplement No.3657);
7. Law No.5 The Year 1997 regarding Psychotropic (State Gazette No.10 the Year 1997, Supplement No.3671) as amended by Law No.11 the Year 2020 regarding Job Creation (State Gazette No.245 the Year 2020, Supplement No.6573);
8. Law No.7 the Year 1997 regarding the Ratification of the United Nations Convention Against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and psychotropic Substances, 1988 (State Gazette No. 17 the Year 1997, Supplement No. 3673);
9. Law No.8 the Year 1999 regarding Consumer Protection (State Gazette No.22 the Year 1999, Supplement No.3821);

10. Law No.30 the Year 1999 regarding Arbitration and Alternative Disputes Resolution (State Gazette No.138 the Year 1999, Supplement No.3872);
11. Law No.39 the Year 1999 regarding Human Rights (State Gazette No.165 the Year 1999, Supplement No.3886);
12. Law No.16 the Year 2001 regarding Foundation (State Gazette No.112 the Year 2001, Supplement No.4132) as amended by Law No.28 the Year 2004 regarding the Amendment of Law No.16 the Year 2001 regarding Foundation (State Gazette No.115 the Year 2004, Supplement No.4430);
13. Law No.29 the Year 2004 regarding Medical Practice (State Gazette No.116 the Year 2004, Supplement No.4431);
14. Law No.40 the Year 2004 regarding National Social Security System (State Gazette No.150 the Year 2004, Supplement No.4456) as amended by Law No.11 the Year 2020 regarding Job Creation (State Gazette No.245 the Year 2020, Supplement No.6573);
15. Law No.44 the Year 2004 regarding Hospital (State Gazette No.153 the Year 2004, Supplement No.5072) as amended by Law No.11 the Year 2020 regarding Job Creation (State Gazette No.245 the Year 2020, Supplement No.6573);
16. Law No.3 the Year 2005 regarding National Sports System (State Gazette No.89 the Year 2005, Supplement No.4535);
17. Law No.40 the Year 2007 regarding Limited Liability Company (State Gazette No.106 the Year 2007, Supplement No.4756);
18. Law No.11 the Year 2008 regarding Electronic Information and Transaction (State Gazette No. 58 the Year 2008 and amended by Law No.19 the Year 2016 regarding the Amendment of Law No.11 the Year 2008 regarding Electronic Information and Transaction (State Gazette No.251 the Year 2016, Supplement No.5952);
19. Law No.35 the Year 2009 regarding Narcotic (State Gazette No.143 the Year 2009, Supplement No.5062) as amended by Law No.11 the Year 2020 regarding Job Creation (State Gazette No.245 the Year 2020, Supplement No.6573);
20. Law No.36 the Year 2009 regarding Health (State Gazette No.144 the Year 2009, Supplement No.5063) as amended by Government Regulation in lieu of Law No.1 the Year 2020 regarding State Financial Policy and Financial System Stability for Handling the Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) Pandemic and/or In Facing Threats that Endanger the National Economy and/or Financial System Stability (State Gazette No.87 the Year 2020, Supplement No.6485) (that has been determined as law based on Law No.2 the Year 2020 regarding the Determination of Government Regulation in lieu of Law No.1 the Year 2020 regarding State Financial Policy and Financial System Stability for Handling the Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) Pandemic and/or In Facing Threats that Endanger the National Economy and/or Financial System Stability as Law (State Gazette No.134 the Year 2020, Supplement No.6516) and Law No.11 the Year 2020 regarding Job Creation (State Gazette No.245 the Year 2020, Supplement No.6573);
21. Law No.24 the Year 2011 regarding Social Health Insurance Administration Body (State Gazette No.116 the Year 2011, Supplement No.5256) as amended by Law No.11 the Year 2020 regarding Job Creation (State Gazette No.245 the Year 2020, Supplement No.6573);
22. Law No.18 the Year 2012 regarding Food (State Gazette No.227 the Year 2012, Supplement No.5360) as amended by Law No.11 the Year 2020 regarding Job Creation (State Gazette No.245 the Year 2020, Supplement No.6573);
23. Law No.20 the Year 2013 regarding Medical Education (State Gazette No.132 the Year 2013, Supplement No.5434);
24. Law No.18 the Year 2014 regarding Mental Health (State Gazette No.185 the Year 2014, Supplement No.5571);
25. Law No.33 the Year 2014 regarding Halal Product Assurance (State Gazette No.295 the Year 2014, Supplement No.5604) as amended by Law No.11 the Year 2020 regarding Job Creation (State Gazette No.245 the Year 2020, Supplement No.6573);
26. Law No.36 the Year 2014 regarding Health Workers (State Gazette No.298 the Year 2014, Supplement No.5607);
27. Law No.38 the Year 2014 regarding Nursing (State Gazette No.307 the Year 2014, Supplement No.5612);
28. Law No.40 the Year 2014 regarding Insurance (State Gazette No.337 the Year 2014, Supplement No.5618);
29. Law No.6 the Year 2018 regarding Health Quarantine (State Gazette No.128 the Year 2018, Supplement No.6236);
30. Law No.4 the Year 2019 regarding Midwifery (State Gazette No.56 the Year 2019, Supplement No.6325);
31. Law No.11 the Year 2019 regarding National System of Science and Technology (State Gazette No.148 the Year 2019) as amended by Law No.11 the Year 2020 regarding Job Creation (State Gazette No.245 the Year 2020, Supplement No.6573).

In research on the secondary legal sources, the researcher found that many books and articles had specifically referred to as medical law, nursing law, midwifery law, sanitarian law, pharmacists law, etcetera. Some are discussing the application of the law only, some are combining with ethical issues, including bioethics. Some publications refer to health law, however, the contents are limited to the discussion of health care services and disputes arising from the services, especially on malpractice from a criminal and civil law perspective.

Results and Discussion

The development of health law in Indonesia has been started when in 1984 in a one-day seminar conducted by Medical Law Review Team, the National Legal Development Agency of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Indonesia in collaboration with PERHUKI and PB IDI, Jakarta (Sampurno, 2011). During the seminar, Van der Mijl (1984) in his paper stated that "...health law as the body of rules that relates directly to the care of health as well as the applications of general civil, criminal, and administrative law." A more broad definition was given by Leenen (1981). He stated that health law is "...the whole of rules of law, directly related to health care and the application of other civil, administrative and criminal law in that regard. This body of legal rules encompasses not only legal law and international law regulations but also international guidelines on customary law and jurisprudential law, while science and literature can also be sources of law." Jayasuriya (1997) identifies that there were at least thirty legislations that can be found concerning health. According to him, in general, from the scope of the health law, the content contained in it is basically to provide protection to individuals, the community, and to facilitate the implementation of health efforts so that health goals can be achieved. Jayasuriya stated that there are five basic functions in health that need to be emphasized. They are the provision of protection, health promotion, health financing, and an assessment of the quantity and quality of health care. Sampurno (2011) in the Final Report of Health Law Compendium Compilation Team summarized that: "Health law is generally regulated in a regulation made based on the public interest. Regulations regarding health are currently regulated in general in Law Number 36 of 2009 regarding Health. The content material contained in Law Number 36 of 2009 concerning Health includes 4 (four) objects, namely: 1. Regulations related to health efforts; 2. Arrangements related to health workers; 3. Arrangements related to health facilities; 4. Regulations related to health commodities."

As can be seen, that the view and attention to health law are much more given to the health care services, the relation between the patient and the health facilities and/ or health workers, which ended in the malpractice, informed consent, forensic science, abortion, euthanasia. Even the relation which involved health workers were reduced to physicians and/ or nurses, meanwhile, according to article 11 of Health Workers Law, there were at least twelve groups of health workers, including medical workers. Health law, in substances, were taught in form of medical law, hospital law, bioethics, medical malpractice law.

Moving from the same direction, the researcher would like to take note of the definition of health. WHO (1976) defines health as "a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being, and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity." Based on the definition, it can be understood that health is not about a clinical issue that determines the characteristics of a physically healthy person. It is also used to define the mental health of a person and the community where the person lived and interacts. It is in line with the content of the Health Law, which regulates physical health, mental health, and community health. From the finding above, it can be seen that Indonesian Government and the House of Representative has issued Mental Health Law. Through content analysis, it can be seen, that in principle the Health Law regulates the following:

1. Principles, purposes, role, obligations, and responsibilities of government in health care;
2. Rights and obligations of individuals, community, and society in health care;
3. Government Institutions involved in health care activities;
4. Health resources, which includes financials or funding, health workers, health supplies, pharmaceutical preparations, medical devices, health care facilities, health technology that will be used to support health efforts conducted by the government;
5. Health efforts, which can be divided into individual health efforts and public health efforts, which can be conducted through promotive, preventive, curative, and rehabilitative health care services;
6. Health information, patient safety, supervision, administrative and penal sanction.

Historically, the Health Law replaced Law No.23 the Year 1992 regarding Health (State Gazette No.100 the Year 1992, Supplement 3494) (the 1992 Health Law), which replaced:

1. Law No.3 the Year 1953 regarding Pharmacy Opening (State Gazette No.18 the Year 1953 No. 18);
2. Law No. 18 the Year 1953 regarding Appointment of Private Hospitals that Care for the Poors and those Financially Incapable (State Gazette No. 48 the Year 1953);
3. Law No. 9 The Year 1960 regarding the Health Main Principles (State Gazette No. 131 the Year 1960, Supplement No. 2068);
4. Law No. 11 The Year 1962 regarding Hygiene for Public Business (State Gazette No. 48 the Year 1962, Supplement No. 2475);

5. Law No. 6 The Year 1963 regarding Health Workers (State Gazette No. 79 the Year 1963, Supplement No. 2576);
6. Law No. 7 The Year 1963 regarding Pharmacy (State Gazette No. 91 the Year 1963, Supplement No. 2580);
7. Law No. 18 The Year 1964 regarding Mandatory Work for Paramedics (State Gazette No. 106 the Year 1964, Supplement No. 2698);
8. Law No. 2 The Year 1966 regarding Hygiene (State Gazette No. 22 the Year 1966, Supplement, No. 2804);
9. Law No. 3 The Year 1966 regarding Mental Health (State Gazette No. 23 the Year 1966, Supplement No. 2805).

If it is historically compared, the Health Law is more comprehensive with all previous laws that regulated health care. Under current health regulations, financial and funding activities become one of the priorities, even there was Law No. 18 the Year 1953. Financial consideration in health care has become a national matter as it is specially made to avoid catastrophic expenditure among those poor and financially incapable people in society. It was then followed by the National Social Security System Law and Social Health Insurance Administration Body Law, which becomes part of the Indonesian National Health System. As stated in the preamble to the 1945 Constitution, the objective of Indonesian legal politics is "to protect the entire Indonesian nation and promote public welfare based on Pancasila."

Health is something related to humans. It is something that cannot be separated from human life. As a living being, everything connected with a human must be known and approved. The human has the autonomy to determine and decide for himself/ herself. No one is more responsible than he/ she is. The understanding of bioethics (Widjaja & Sijabat, 2020) and its relation to health law and bioethics will explain the very basic knowledge about health care. Health care activities are actions that require the involvement of bioethics, competency, and legal authority. Health care activities require zero error tolerance. It will introduce how the health care activities shall be conducted. Bioethics is not only for health workers that contact directly during providing health care services, but also every health worker. Even pharmacists who work in the industry must comply with bioethical principles (Widjaja, 2019b).

To understand how health care works, a comprehensive understanding of health care institutions that are involved in all aspects of health care activities must be known and understood. Currently, there are at least twelve official government institutions and organizations that are involved directly with health care activities. They are:

1. *Kementerian Kesehatan* (the Ministry of Health);
2. *Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Sosial* (Social Health Insurance Administration Body);
3. *Badan Pengawas Obat dan Makanan* (Indonesian Food and Drug Authority);
4. *Konsil Kedokteran Indonesia* (Indonesian Medical Council);
5. *Konsil Tenaga Kesehatan Indonesia* (Indonesian Health Workers Council);
6. *Badan Nasional Penanggulangan Bencana* (National Board for Disaster Management);
7. *Badan Kependudukan Dan Keluarga Berencana Nasional* (National Population and Family Planning Agency);
8. *Badan Narkotika Nasional* (National Anti Narcotics Agency);
9. *Komisi Etik Penelitian Dan Pengembangan Kesehatan Nasional* (National Health Research and Development Ethics Commission);
10. *Badan Penyelesaian Sengketa Konsumen* (Consumer Dispute Settlement Agency);
11. *Badan Pengawas Rumah Sakit Provinsi* (Provincial Hospital Supervisory Agency);
12. *Badan Pertimbangan Kesehatan Nasional Pusat* (Central National Health Advisory Agency);

Each body, agency, or institution has its function and role. Any deviation, violation, incident, incompliance, misconduct, or any event concerning the health care situations, including health care services, either individual health or public health must be reported to the authorized organization. Therefore the understanding of the function and legal authority of each organization is a must. Besides, there are also the professional organizations of each health worker, health facilities, health collegium, health institutions that take care of its members' conducts. In current practice, there are many government agencies, as stated above that have not functionally performed to their optimum capacity. Some of them have never been heard by the public in general. By understanding their existences, their roles can be optimized for the benefit of human health in general. There were also even, whereby the institution has made regulations that raised debates if it has reduced the right of the people (Widjaja, 2018a) and the competencies of pharmacists in community health center (Saputra & Widjaja, 2021).

Under current laws, there is only one law that regulated health facilities, i.e. Hospital law. Other health facilities are regulated in the Minister of Health Decree. To make a health facility works, there were external regulations and internal regulations. The external regulation will tell the government and private investors how to establish a health facility, what is the most suitable forms of the organization (company, foundation, association, venture) of the health facility that will be established, what kind of permits, licenses, and other administrative requirements that are needed to run the hospital. The internal regulations (by-laws) will consist of

corporate by-laws, which regulate the internal organizational structure of the health facility, their function, roles, responsibilities, accountabilities, and how are they related to one another; and the clinical framework through which health facility provides its health services while continuously improving the quality and safeguarding patient safety (Widjaja, 2020a).

The legislation concerning hospitals as one of the health facilities is well regulated, but not with the others. There is a Minister of Health decree on hospital by-laws, as internal regulation for hospitals, but the understanding of the requirement and existence of hospital by-laws was not known very well (Widjaja & Permanasari, 2016). Many disputes related to the hospital and the health worker that works in the hospital, however, the hospital by-law was never used as a tool for settling the disputes (Susanti & Widjaja, 2021). The division of hospital by-laws into corporate by-laws and clinical by-laws was never clearly explained. The function of clinical by-laws was rarely, or even never been explained as part of informed consent. Therefore for those who would understand on how hospital and other health facilities works must know and understand the external and internal regulations of the health facilities.

The Government of the Republic of Indonesia has promulgated four laws that govern health workers. They are the Medical Practice Law that regulated the practice of physician; Health Workers Law that regulated all health workers profession in general; the Nursing Law and the Midwifery Law that specially regulated the nursing practice and midwife profession. Besides those laws, there is one government regulation that governs the pharmaceutical practice by pharmacists. The existence of other health workers is regulated by the Minister of Health Regulations.

These health workers can work in the health facility or outside the health facility. The latest is known as solo and group practice. In any way of the practices, the health workers need to have the competency and authority to provide the health services before they can legally become health professionals according to their specialty. Each type of health worker has an organization that can provide the certification, license, and permit to practice, including the way to punish and provide sanctions to those who do not comply and follow the rules, guidance, and instructions.

Medical intervention cannot be separated from medicine or drugs or pharmaceutical preparation. There are Good Manufacturing Practices, Good Distribution Practices, Good Transportation Practices, Good Warehousing Practices, and Good Clinical Practices that are required to have good, sounding medicine. A National Agency will be assigned to release the drugs for consummation and at the same time monitoring the post-marketing for un-identified or unintended adverse effects. Each channel of distribution from the manufacturer, distributor, retailer, either the hospital pharmacy installation, drug store, or pharmacy, until it reaches the patient, must be well managed. Each permit, license, and certification must be well inspected. Under current regulations, the Good Transportation Practices (Widjaja, 2018b) and Good Warehousing Practices are embodied in Good Distribution Practices and Good Manufacturing Practices. Those are needed to provide an economic, clinical, and humanistic outcome for the patients. Drugs are not supposed to be clinically effective, but they shall also be cost-effective, cost-benefit, and cost-utility. Finally, the consumed drugs must be humanistic. There are drugs that can be freely bought, some must be prescribed, some need special treatment, and many other kinds of drugs. Each needs specific treatment whenever it is delivered to a patient. Drugs information has become important. Patient counseling, education, and communications are a must before a patient consumed the drugs.

As a country with muslim majority, halal has become another issue in food, drugs, and other kinds of products that may be used or consumed. Food and drugs regulations may be clear. However, the use of alcohol in cosmetics is still ambiguous. There is alcohol that it's used may penetrate human skin or due to accidental inhalation can enter the blood, and alcohol that never penetrates the human body. Detail regulations must be further discussed (Widjaja & Sijabat, 2021a).

Besides drugs, food and beverages must be regulated also. As something that enters the human body, food, and beverages, including other kinds of objects, they need to be un-harmful to people. Legal and administrative measures shall be taken to make sure that the food and beverages comply with the given standard.

As mentioned before health workers can provide health care services inside or outside the health facility. The health care services provided by each kind of health worker will be different from the others. The duty, obligation, role, and responsibility of a physician will different from a nurse, midwife, pharmacist, and other health workers. In principle the services provided by the health workers shall be made in a contract, which can be orally made and/ or written in one or more documents. Understanding general contract law and specific health care services contracts would be useful avoid and or settle any differences, conflicts, and disputes in the future.

Consent under the health law is not just a usual consent. It is informed consent, that refers to the principle of autonomy in bioethics. Health information is asymmetric between health workers and patients. It is, therefore, communication and education must be given to the patient so that the patient can make a "legal" decision based on the information. Sometimes consent is not only needed for any (clinical) services provided by

the health worker, consent for administrative services provided by the health facility, and matters concerning the clinical activities must also be given by the patient and/ or the close family of the patient. Each legal relation must be well considered that can be used to seek responsibilities and accountabilities from the default parties, that the laymen as malpractice.

Abortion and euthanasia are prohibited conduct. It shall not be conducted by any person, especially health workers. Under the Indonesian Penal Code, there is an additional penal sanction for a physician who conducts or assists the process of abortion or euthanasia. However, there are the Minister of Health Regulations which, under certain circumstances and with the fulfillment of certain conditions, abortion and euthanasia may be conducted. Under the Minister of Health Regulations, abortion can be done by a physician that fulfills the requirements stated in the regulation. Pharmacists can assist the legal abortion in compliance with the regulation (Widjaja, 2019a).

Many public health issues, like isolation, quarantine, and social distancing obligation during the Covid-19 pandemic, the requirement to have Covid-19 vaccination, and many other prohibitions following the Covid-19 Pandemic are issues that are treated as reducing freedom as parts of basic human rights. Many people refused to follow the government's instructions. Even in certain areas, conflict happened between the government and some of the people. These issues must be settled with local wisdom meanwhile keeping the main objective in protecting the interest of public health. The public health office and society must be able to identify and settle the most crucial and important issues. Otherwise, the policies and the issued legislations will only create other kinds of public issues (Widjaja & Sijabat, 2021b). Concerning the issue of isolation and quarantine, Indonesia has promulgated the Health Quarantine Law, but the Law was never put in place (Widjaja, 2020b). The issue of "mandatory" vaccination in Indonesia has been discussed (Aini & Widjaja (2021).

Narcotics, tobacco, and alcohol are the other public matters that have not been yet settled. Each of them may have benefits. However, the harm that is caused by using narcotics, tobacco, and alcohol is more dangerous. The making of the legislation against the use of narcotics, tobacco, and alcohol must consider the possible use in maintaining health and/ or as substances used in the healing process. Public health law becomes a separate course subject that must be well understood, not only for public health experts but also for lawyers who are interested in handling public health issues. Until today the debate of the use of Cannabis for medical use in Indonesia remained (Widjaja, 2018c) (Idham & Widjaja, 2021).

There are other public health issues, such as sports, occupational health and safety, and environmental health have been developed in other fields of learning. Each has become and practically belongs to other subjects. Sports law has become part of the sports school. Occupational health and safety law is taught as part of employment law. Meanwhile, the environmental health law has long been part of environmental law.

Almost the same as sports law, health insurance law has been taught in insurance law. However, due to the specific regulations on health financing through National Social Security System, health insurance law must be taught side by side with the National Social Security System. The health insurance program becomes part of the National Social Security System that may be used for the best benefit of the people. The current issue that has become a concern for the public is the use of state funds to finance the effect of Covid-19. Until today there is no clear regulation on the accountability of the use of the fund (Rahmayani & Widjaja, 2021).

Malpractice as part of the health care services can cause many consequences. Apart from the administrative sanction and civil lawsuit for legal and equitable remedies, in some events, a penal sanction can be imposed. Since there is general criminal law (the Indonesian Penal Code), and specific criminal law in other laws (as mentioned above) that provide penal sanction, the application and implementation of the laws must be well and fully attended to. As mentioned above, abortion in the Indonesian Penal Code is prohibited but in Health Law there is a possibility for legal abortion. The same applies to euthanasia. It is therefore comprehensive understanding of the applicable law is a must.

Another issue is about the chemical castration sanction that was imposed by the judges in the court of law on criminals who committed child sexual crimes. The issue arose because the medical doctors who are responsible to carry out the chemical castration refuse to do it. Even there is a government regulation that regulates chemical castration, debates around the detail of the process are still continuous (Efiyanti & Widjaja, 2021).

The Health Law also regulates the use of technology in many ways. It could be in the way the health care services are being conducted; the way it used to produce health resources, such as food, pharmaceutical products, and medical devices; public health utilities; health information records, and other things that related to the use of technology and technology products to support health care in Indonesia. Especially during the Covid-19 pandemic, the use of information technology is very helpful. Some health care activities that are not recommended to be conducted face to face can be conducted using the assistance of technology products.

Health technology is something tremendously developed in the last 21st century. The development of science in technology, especially artificial intelligence has made some research that was deemed to be impossible become reality. Cryptography as a way to secure data and digital ledger technology as a way to store data has created Big Data sources. The technology has developed in a way that health data and information that

were kept in a so-called (e-)medical record can be saved and retrieved at any time and anywhere by the authorized person only. Data leaked and cybercrime become new modes of criminal acts that must be resolved internationally.

Health technology is also used to provide an economic, clinical, and humanistic outcome for all interventions to the patients, including the finding of new drugs. The clinical trials used to find clinically effective and safe drugs is now incorporate economic value, which at least will create the cost-effective drugs. Indonesia has issued a decree of the use of pharmacoeconomics to have one cost-effective drug within many similar drugs. However, until today, it was not been nationally conducted. Only certain hospital has made the trials (Widjaja & Sijabat, 2019).

Another matter that must also be attended to is the use of medical science in solving criminal issues in law. Forensic medicine has grown to become a specialized course in medical school. The combination of knowledge of criminal law and medical science has been learned a long time ago and until today it is still one of several preferred disciplines in medical school.

As noted that malpractice in health care services can be caused and/ or related to several aspects. There are ethical issues, discipline and competency matters, and legal problems, especially about civil remedies which will be conducted in a civil lawsuit. The administrative and penal sanctions will be taken care of by the state through the police department. Today, the three kinds of enforcement are applied. Ethical issues will be settled by each professional organization where the health workers belong. Discipline and competency matters will be reviewed by the Indonesian Medical Discipline Honorary Council, an independent body within Indonesian Medical Council for physicians and dentists; and each health worker's council under Indonesian Health Workers Council.

The decision of the Indonesian Medical Discipline Honorary Council, an independent body within the Indonesian Medical Council for physicians and dentists, in its which stated "breach under this decision cannot be treated as '*culpa*' (fault) or '*opzet*' (*intent*), or '*opzet bij mogelijkheid*' (intent by possibility) and tort, in a criminal act (*waderechtig*) or civil suit (*onrechtmatigedaad*) in the meaning of unlawful medical malpractice" is unnecessary. Moreover, the statement that the Indonesian Medical Discipline Honorary Council cannot be used as evidence in the court of law is misleading. The decision of the Medical Discipline Honorary Council as long as it fulfills the requirements under the procedural law can always be used as evidence or at least sufficient preliminary evidence in the court of law. Either it is in a criminal court of law or civil suit. It is merely sufficient that people understand that the Indonesian Medical Discipline Honorary Council only has competencies in discipline and competency matters for the physician and dentists profession.

The civil lawsuit will be settled through the court of law. It is not about physicians or hospitals with the patient, but for all health workers, including nurses (Widjaja & Sijabat, 2017). The Health Law opens the possibility to use mediation to settle civil disputes (Widjaja, 2020c). This, however, does not limit the possibility to settle health care disputes through arbitration (Widjaja & Ayuningtyas, 2015). It is all, in general, regulated in Law No.30 the Year 1999 regarding Arbitration and Alternative Disputes Resolution.

At last, it should be noted that the lawyer need not know or understand the whole process but should know the flow of the process. The lawyer shall understand and make sure that each step has been conducted and all necessary step has been taken. The collaboration between lawyers and health professionals will certainly support the development of health law education and regulation towards better health for everybody and the community.

Conclusion and Recommendations

From the analysis over the content analysis using the grounded theory, the researcher is in the opinion, that health law shall at least provide knowledge on the following aspects or fields:

1. Introduction to health law and bioethics;
2. Health sector institutions;
3. Law concerning health care facilities;
4. Law concerning personnel and health professions;
5. Law of food and drug control and administration;
6. Legal health care services;
7. Community health law;
8. Sports law;
9. Occupational safety and health;
10. Environmental health;
11. Law of health financing and insurance;
12. Health Technology;
13. Health and human rights
14. Health criminal and forensic law;
15. Health dispute settlement and health profession court.

Each of the fields will provide legal knowledge on every aspect of health law. Some of them are not a new course in legal aspects but it needs to be conducted comprehensively to have comprehensive knowledge of health law. This will enforce the comprehensive amendment of current legislation in health law. A new omnibus law in the field of health law may become new agenda.

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The research may be conducted in other states and countries and the researcher is open to further discussions of the new paradigm in health law education. This may lead to the universal law of health.

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